

Nutritional aspects of *Gryllus bimaculatus*: an alternative traditional food in tribal communities in Assam, India

Jayanta Kr. Das^{a*}

^aAssistant Professor (Selection Grade) Department of Zoology, Barama College, Baksa, BTR, Assam

Received: Dec 15, 2025

Accepted: Jan 05, 2026

Published: Jan 16, 2026

Abstract: Edible insects are an affordable source of protein and a traditional super food for tribal communities in Northeast India and abroad. The insects like silkworm pupae, giant water bugs, grasshoppers, termites, and crickets are being popular delicacy which are eaten fried, roasted, or in form of chutney. Insect consumption as a substitute for conventional diets is linked to global food security. Insects, particularly crickets are rich in nutrients and can serve as alternative sources of proteins, lipids, and micronutrients. The present study recorded significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) concentrations of moisture and lipid in female *G. bimaculatus* as 70.45 ± 1.09 g/100g and 11.90 ± 1.20 g/100g. While no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed in values of protein and carbohydrate content in both male and female samples of the species. This study investigated the antioxidant properties of *G. bimaculatus* obtained from a local market in Assam, India. The results showed high antioxidant activity, with total phenolic content recorded as 65.32 ± 1.28 mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/100g, total flavonoid content as 18.06 ± 1.08 mg quercetin equivalent (QE)/100g, and DPPH radical scavenging activity as $85.42 \pm 2.15\%$. The findings of this work support *G. bimaculatus* as a valuable and health-promoting alternative nutrient source for animal feed.

Keywords: affordable, antioxidant activity, edible, health-promoting, protein, traditional

I. INTRODUCTION

Edible insects are a sustainable natural food for people all over the world. Entomophagy is an age-old practice in the North-eastern region of India. The tribal people in their locality consume insects and their larvae based on their tastiness and therapeutic uses. Many edible insects have been used traditionally in folk medicine. Numerous ethnic communities worldwide have long embraced the consumption of insects as part of their daily diet. Entomophagy is recognized in approximately 110 countries, with around 2,100 insect species being consumed as food globally [1]. The preparation and consumption methods for insects vary across regions, influenced by cultural diversity, availability, and local consumption habits. Insects offer a rich source of nutrients and essential elements necessary for growth and development. Many researchers have extensively documented the abundant nutrient content present in

insects. These tiny creatures are enriched with proteins, amino acids, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, minerals, trace elements, and possess antioxidant potential [2-7]. As a result, insects hold significant nutritional and medicinal importance. Tribal people in Assam including a few non-tribal people accept insects as food for their high nutritional value. The eating habits of these people help to fight malnutrition and food insecurity. Edible insects are linked to various cultural beliefs of the ethnic people in Assam, India. Recognizing its potential, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations promoted entomophagy as a healthy food choice for humans in 2013 [8]. The FAO also acknowledged insect farming as a sustainable and eco-friendly practice, further endorsing the utilization of insects as a viable and beneficial food source. Entomophagy has a long-standing history in India, with a wide variety of edible insect species being found in the country. In fact, there are approximately 255 edible insect species documented in India, and entomophagy is particularly prevalent among the tribal communities of North-East India [9-10]. For these ethnic communities, entomophagy is deeply intertwined with their cultural and culinary heritage, and it also holds significance within their traditional medicinal practices [11]. Assam, specifically, is home to a rich diversity of edible insects, with nearly 67 species belonging to 27 families and 8 orders being identified in the region [12-17]. The tribal communities in Assam consume insects from various orders, including Orthoptera, Coleoptera, Lepidoptera, Hymenoptera, and Isoptera [15, 18,19].

Crickets are a group of insects belonging to the order Orthoptera. These species of insects are very much beneficial in terms of nutritional value, ethnomedicine, livelihood improvement and feed for livestock. Edible crickets are nutritionally enriched with proteins (55-73%), lipids (4.30-33.44%), vitamins such as A, B group, C, D, E and K and different mineral elements such as calcium, potassium, magnesium, iron, copper, zinc, sodium etc. Around the world approximately 60 different cricket species are consumed [6]. In many countries these species are farmed economically [20]. The role of crickets however as food and feed as well as boosting the economy and improving livelihood is crucial. In North-East India especially in Assam, many species of crickets such as, *Tarbinskiellus portentosus*, *Schizodactylus monstrosus*, *Gryllus bimaculatus*, *Acheta domesticus*, *Gryllotalpa affricana* etc. are consumed by different tribal communities [15, 18,19]. Despite the popularity of consuming crickets within tribal communities, works regarding nutritional composition, antioxidant properties, element composition are still limited. Scientific validation is necessary to confirm their rich nutrient content and their potential as a food source. This study aims to provide scientific evidence on the antioxidant activities of *G. bimaculatus*. Although the nutritional composition and mineral content of this species have been reported by Udomsil *et al.* [20], the present study seeks to contribute additional data to further validate its use as food and feed. Thus, this work aims to investigate and assess the antioxidant properties of *G. bimaculatus* and explore their potential health benefits.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Collection, identification and preservation of *Gryllus bimaculatus*

Exclusive field surveys were conducted in the locality of the tribal dominated villages of BTAD region in Assam. Insects were collected using entomological nets, beating tray, water traps, or through digging and handpicking.

On the basis of the information collected from the local people, *Gryllus bimaculatus* was purchased from the local markets of different districts in Assam. Insects were taken to the laboratory in air-tight sterilized collecting jars for identification, preservation and further analysis was carried out in the Zoology department, Cotton University and Barama College, Barama. A few collected insects were processed for preservation following the method of ARC-PPRI (1996) and provided to the Department of Zoology, Barama College as museum specimens. Identification of the insects was performed in the Department of Zoology, Barama College by using a taxonomic key.

B. Tissue Processing for Biochemical Assay:

Before chemical analysing freezer samples were washed with distilled water and kept in room temperature for a few hours. For chemical analysis, adult and healthy insects were selected. 10% tissue homogenate was prepared by mixing 1 gram of insect in 10 ml of phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) using a tissue homogenizer. The homogenate was centrifuged at 6,000 rpm for 10 min using a centrifuge machine. The supernatant was collected and used as tissue source for biochemical analysis.

The protein content of the edible insects was estimated following the method of Lowry et al. [21] method using bovine serum albumin as a standard protein. Estimation of carbohydrate was done by following Anthrone method [22]. The total lipid was estimated using chloroform methanol method described by Folch *et al.* [23]. The soluble protein, lipid and carbohydrate contents present in edible insects is expressed in g per gm in fresh weight as shown in Table 1 (Values are represented as \pm standard deviation).

C. Sample preparation for moisture content and assess the antioxidant activities

The collected insects were initially killed by freezing them at 0°C and subsequently subjected to thorough washing. Next, the insects were gutted, and their wings and legs were removed. The remaining edible portion was weighed and subjected to sun-drying and oven-drying at 103°C for duration of four hours. Once completely dried, the samples were cooled in a desiccator, finely powdered, and re-weighed [5, 7]. The resulting powder was used to determine the moisture content and assess the antioxidant activities, including %DPPH inhibition, total phenolic content and total flavonoid content.

D. Moisture content

Moisture content of the insect was determined by using protocol described by AOAC [24]

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight of sample taken}} \times 100$$

E. Total phenol content (TPC)

TPC was estimated by following works of Singleton *et al.* [25] and Ordonez *et al.* [26]. TPC was expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/100g.

F. Total flavonoid content (TFC)

TFC was estimated following the methods of Ordonez *et al.* [26], Woisky *et al.* [27], Chang *et al.* [28]. TFC was expressed as mg quercetin equivalent (QE)/100g.

G. DPPH Scavenging activity assay

2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Radical Scavenging Activity was determined by following the protocol of Mamta *et al.* [29] and Pant *et al.* [30]. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard to measure the activity at 517 nm in a spectrophotometer and the scavenging activity of *G. bimaculatus* was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{DPPH Scavenging Activity (\%)} = \{[\text{Abs}_{\text{control}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{sample}}] / \text{Abs}_{\text{control}}\} \times 100$$

Where, $\text{Abs}_{\text{control}}$ = Absorbance of DPPH in Methanol

$\text{Abs}_{\text{sample}}$ = Absorbance of DPPH in sample extract

H. Statistical analysis

All the data for analysis were presented as Mean±Standard Deviation (SD) and performed in triplicates. (n=3). Student's t-test was performed where two means were involved. The analysis was carried out in Past 4.17 free software.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the study period, information shared by the local people and market vendors selling *G. bimaculatus* revealed the popularity of this species as 'edible' among different tribal communities; Bodo, Rabha etc. The vernacular (Bodo) name of the species within the collection site is '*Fenda dangra*'. The species is active during summer and mostly abundant at night. For harvesting, different techniques such as pouring water into holes and burrows, light or lamp traps, and handpicking are used. Insects are first degutted followed by removal of wings and then roasted for consumption. Removal of legs for consumption is optional. Although, apart from consumption, these insects are collected and used as bait for hook and line, which is very popular among people of all age groups.

Table 1: Proximate composition of male and female of *G. bimaculatus*

Proximate composition	<i>G. bimaculatus</i>		p value
	Male	Female	
Moisture content (g/100g)	64.65±1.34 ^a	70.45±1.09 ^b	p<0.05
Protein content (g/100g)	18.90±2.01 ^a	16.50±1.59 ^a	p>0.05
Lipid content (g/100g)	6.50±1.03 ^a	11.90±1.20 ^b	p<0.05
Carbohydrate content (g/100g)	5.81±1.55 ^a	5.35±1.31 ^a	p>0.05

*Values are mean of three replicates and expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD)

[#]Different superscripts along the row differ significantly.

On chemical analysis it was observed that orthopteran edible insects are nutritious in terms of protein. The present study revealed significantly higher (p<0.05) concentrations of moisture and lipid in female *G. bimaculatus* as 70.45±1.09 g/100g and 11.90±1.20 g/100g respectively (Table 1). While no significant differences (p>0.05) were observed in values of protein and carbohydrate content and were found to range from 16.50±1.59 to 18.90±2.01 g/100g and 5.35±1.31 to 5.81±1.55 g/100g respectively (Table 1).

As for example, Mole crickets, Cricket and all the species of Grasshoppers have high protein and lipid and considerable amount of carbohydrate. Therefore, these insect species may be good source of nutritious food to promote in areas of food insecurity and malnutrition. However, nutrient composition is only a proxy for effects on human health, and this is a significant limitation of the present study.

Likewise, essential antioxidant properties were also studied where phenolic and flavonoid contents were recorded as 65.32±1.28 mg GAE/100gm and 18.06±1.08 mg QE/100gm respectively. On the other-hand, DPPH scavenging activity was recorded in higher percentage (85.42±2.15%) in *G. bimaculatus* (Table 2).

Table 2: Biochemical nutritional composition of *G. bimaculatus*

Biochemical and Nutritional indices	<i>G. bimaculatus</i> adult worker
Total Phenol content (mg GAE/100gm)	65.32±1.28
Total flavonoid content (mg QE/100gm)	18.06±1.08
DPPH scavenging percentage (%)	85.42±2.15

Values are mean of three replicates and expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD)

*d.w.: dry weight; results obtained after drying at 103°C.

The remarkable nutritional composition of insects positions them as an exceptional source of energy. Globally, around 2 billion people consume insects as a food source, highlighting the potential of entomophagy as an alternative solution to address the global food crisis. In addition to their role as food, many insect species are also utilized in traditional medicinal systems. They are enriched with proteins, carbohydrates, fats, amino acids, trace elements, vitamins, and minerals. While previous research has focused on analyzing the nutritional composition of

various insects, studies on their antioxidant activities have been limited. In a study by Soren *et al.* [5] proximate composition and mineral content of two cricket species viz; *T. portentosus* and *S. monstrosus* collected from Assam were estimated. Another similar study by Udomsil *et al.* [20] described the rich nutrient composition, mineral content, functional properties, fatty acid and amino acid composition of *Acheta domesticus* and *Gryllus bimaculatus*. These studies have highlighted the rich nutrient composition of orthopterans, particularly crickets. However, specific estimations related to the antioxidant activities of *G. bimaculatus* are lacking. Presence of antioxidants in diet is advantageous for humans. Antioxidant components strengthen the body's immune responses, therefore enhance resistance. Antioxidant molecules can neutralize free radicals or reactive oxygen species (ROS) which are produced during biological metabolism of the body. One of the prominent pathways of neutralizing free radicals is scavenging where chain reactions of free radicals are interrupted by different phenolic compounds present in a sample [31]. Phenolic compounds can hamper free radicals through their redox properties [7, 31]. However, the level of phenolic compounds should not exceed its minimum lethal dose (70 mg/kg for adults). In the present study, phenolic content is recorded 65.32 ± 1.28 mg GAE/100gm. The content of total phenolics recorded in this study is found less as compared to lethal oral dose making it safer for human consumption. Flavonoids are other important compounds necessary for human health. These compounds possess important medicinal benefits such as anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer and antiviral properties along with neuro and cardio-protective effects [32]. The flavonoid content recorded in this study is 18.06 ± 1.08 mg QE/100gm. In the present study, high percentage of DPPH scavenging activity is recorded ($85.42 \pm 2.15\%$) indicating high antioxidant potential of *G. bimaculatus*. The present study can be compared with other available literature in order to understand the antioxidant potentiality of *G. bimaculatus*. A study by Sarmah *et al.* [7] revealed DPPH-scavenging activity, total phenolic and flavonoid content of five commonly available aquatic insects of Assam viz; *Litocerus indicus*, *Diplonychus rusticus*, *Cybister* sp, *Laccotrephes* sp and *Ranatra* sp. The study showed DPPH-scavenging activity, total phenolic and flavonoid content within a range of 117.39 to 363.80 mg Catechol equivalent/100 g, 17.70 to 50.82 mg Quercetin equivalent/100g and 80.82 to 91.47 % respectively. The results of the present study are found consistent with the works of Sarmah *et al.* [7]. *G. bimaculatus* is commonly consumed among tribal communities in the collected area due to its availability, low cost, and ease of harvesting. Moreover, its consumption helps control insect populations, preventing pest attacks. With its rich nutrient composition and antioxidant activity, *G. bimaculatus* proves to be an excellent alternative energy source, particularly during food crises and for addressing malnutrition in rural and marginalized societies. Its potential as a fish meal also shows promise in enhancing the growth and feed efficiency of marine finfish species olive flounder, *Paralichthys olivaceus* [33].

In the study by Wang *et al.* [34] reported that on the nutritional value of field cricket (*Gryllus testaceus*) has high value as poultry feed. The present study on the Orthopteran species shows a variation among the species. It can be reported that most of Orthopteran insects are rich source of protein which was found to have 8.2 gm to 24.6 gm per 100 gm fresh body weight. Thus, insects represent the cheapest source of animal protein in the study region and that their consumption should be encouraged because many of the people cannot afford fish or other meat due to high price. There is need for well-documentation of traditional rearing, cultivation and sustainable use of edible insects for the greater benefit of our future generation and maintenance of insect bio-diversity. Overall, results of the present

study provided additional evidence for the potential value of *G. bimaculatus* as a food source, particularly consumable levels of total phenolic content and high DPPH scavenging activity. It suggests *G. bimaculatus* could have health benefits beyond their nutritional value.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study showed the remarkable macronutrient contents such as protein, lipid and carbohydrate as well as antioxidant activity of *G. bimaculatus*. From chemical point of view, it is establishing as a highly beneficial edible insect with significant potential for enhancing human health. The findings not only reinforce the existing understanding of its exceptional nutritional profile but also provide a strong basis for future research aimed at fully exploring its utilization as a viable food source. However, further studies are needed to comprehensively evaluate its suitability for large-scale production and widespread consumption. Continued investigation into the diverse benefits and implications of incorporating *G. bimaculatus* into our diets is crucial for addressing food security challenges and promoting sustainable nutrition practices.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Author is grateful to the Department of Zoology, Barama College as well as Cotton University, Assam for providing the necessary laboratory facilities for this work. The author is also thankful to the local people for sharing valuable information regarding the experimental species. The author is extremely grateful to Dr. Karabi Kalita, Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Barama College. Barama for her sincere support.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Jongema Y. (2017). Worldwide list of recorded edible insects. The Netherlands: Department of Entomology, Wageningen University and Research.
2. Banjo AD, Lawal OA, Songonuga EA. (2006). The nutritional value of fourteen species of edible insects in southwestern Nigeria. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5: 298-301. <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJB>
3. Narzari S, Sarmah, J. (2015). Proximate composition of wild edible insects consumed by the Bodo tribe of Assam, India. *International Journal of Bioassays*, 4:4050-4054. <https://www.ijbio.com/articles/>
4. Bhattacharyya B, Choudhury B, Das P, Dutta, SK, Bhagawati S, Pathak K. (2018). Nutritional composition of five soil-dwelling scarab beetles (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae) of Assam, India. *Coleoptera Bulletin*, 72:339-346. <https://doi.org/10.1649/0010-065X-72.2.339>
5. Soren DA, Choudhury K, Saprana JP, Sarma D. (2021). Nutrient and toxic heavy metal assessment of *Tarbinskiellus portentosus* and *Schizodactylus monstrosus* consumed by the Bodo tribe in Assam, India. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 41: 2001-2006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-021-00439-1>

6. Magara OJH, Niassy S, Ayieko AM, Mukundamago M, Egonyu PJ. et al. (2021). Edible crickets (Orthoptera) around the world: distribution, nutritional value and other benefits - A review. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 7:537915. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2020.537915>
7. Sarmah M, Bhattacharyya B, Bhagawati S, Sarmah K. (2022). Nutritional composition of some commonly available aquatic edible insects of Assam, India. *Insects*, 13: 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects13110976>
8. Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). (2013). Edible insects: Future prospects for food and feed security. Forestry Paper 171, pp. 1-154. <https://www.fao.org/3/i3253e/i3253e.pdf>
9. Chakravorty J. (2014). Diversity of edible insects and practices of entomophagy in India: An overview. *Journal of Biodiversity Bioprospecting and Development*, 1: 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2376-0214.1000124>
10. Loganatban R, Haldhar MS. (2020). Utilization of edible insects as food in North East India. *Indian Entomologist*, 1: 25-31. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343523563>
11. Mozhui L, Kakati NL, Kiewhuo P, Changhija S. (2020). Traditional knowledge of the utilization of edible insects in Nagaland, North-East India. *Foods*, 9: 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9070852>
12. Ronghang R, Ahmed R. (2010). Edible insects and their conservation strategy in Karbi Anglong district of Assam, North East India. *The Bioscan*, 2: 515-521. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/EDIBLE-INSECTS-AND-THEIR-CONSERVATION-STRATEGY-IN-Ronghang-Ahmed/01d89bae32f8639d85b5a9d374ed6396ca467483>
13. Doley AK, Kalita J. (2012). Traditional uses of insect and insect products in medicine and food by the Mishing tribe of Dhemaji District, Assam, North-East India. *Social Science Researcher*, 1: 11-21. http://ssrn.com/issue/volOne/1_2_2.pdf
14. Das JK, Hazarika AK. (2012). Nutritional value of some edible insects in Baksa District, BTAD, Assam. *The Clarion*, 1: 112-115. <https://clarion.ind.in/index.php/clarion/article/view/29/43>
15. Narzari S, Sarmah J. (2015). A study on the prevalence of entomophagy among the Bodos of Assam. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 3(2): 315-320. <https://www.entomoljournal.com/archives/2015/vol3issue2/PartF/3-3-5.pdf>
16. Hazarika HN. (2018). Entomology with special reference to Assam. *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application and Management*, 4: 458-462. <https://doi.org/10.18231/2454-9150.2018.0526>
17. Rahman A, Bordoloi S, Mazid S. (2018). Entomophagy practiced among the Tiwa community of Morigaon district, Assam. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 6: 484-486. <https://www.entomoljournal.com/archives/2018/vol6issue1/PartG/5-6-270-468.pdf>
18. Das KJ. (2021). Entomophagy, a way of food sustainability amongst the tribal people in Baksa district, Assam, India. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 9(1): 2320-2882. www.ijcrt.org/IJCRT2111031
19. Kalita T, Sharma R, Sengupta S, Basumatari D. (2022). Entomology practices in Bodoland Territorial Region, Assam: nutritional potential and implications for food security. *Journal of Insects as Food and Feed*, 8(12): 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2021.0141>

20. Udomsil N, Imsoonthornruksa S, Gosalawit C, Ketudat-Cairns. (2019). Nutritional values and functional properties of house cricket (*Acheta domesticus*) and field cricket (*Gryllus bimaculatus*). *Food Science and Technology Research*, 25(4): 597-605. <https://doi.org/10.3136/fstr.25.597>
21. Lowry OH, Rosebrough NJ, Farr AL, Randall RJ. (1951). Protein measurement with the Folin phenol reagent. *J Biol Chem*, 193(1): 265-275.
22. Sadasivam S, Manickam A. (2008). *Biochemical methods*. New Age International Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi.
23. Folch J, Lees M, Stanley GS. (1957). A simple method for the isolation and purification of total lipides from animal tissues. *Journal of biological chemistry*, 226(1): 497-509.
24. Association of Official Analytical Chemists. 1999. *Official Methods of Analysis*. AOAC, Washington, DC.
25. Singleton LV, Orthofer R, Lamuela-Raventos MR. (1999). Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. *Methods in Enzymology*, 299: 152-178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879\(99\)99017-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879(99)99017-1)
26. Ordonez AAL, Gomez JG, Vattuone MA, Isla MI. (2006). Antioxidant activities of *Sechium edule* (Jacq.) Swart extracts. *Food Chemistry*, 97: 452-458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2005.05.024>
27. Woisky RG, Salatino A. (1998). Analysis of propolis: some parameters and procedures for chemical quality control. *Journal of Apicultural Research*, 37: 9-105. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00218839.1998.11100961>
28. Chang C, Yang M, Wen H, Chern J. (2002). Estimation of total flavonoid content in propolis by two complementary colorimetric methods. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis*, 10: 178-182. <https://doi.org/10.38212/2224-6614.2748>
29. Mamta MS, Amitabh KV, Vats P, Nandi SP, Negi PS, Misra K. (2015). Phytochemical and antimicrobial activities of Himalayan *Cordyceps sinensis* (Berk.) Sacc. *Indian J Exp Biol*, 53(1): 36-43. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25675710/>
30. Pant G, Simaria C, Varsi HAR, Bhan P, Sibi G. (2015). In vitro anti-cholesterol and antioxidant activity of methanolic extracts from flex seeds (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Research Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 9: 300-306. <https://doi.org/10.17311/rjmp.2015.300.306>
31. Swargiary A, Daimari A, Daimari M, Basumatary N, Narzary E. (2016). Phytochemicals, antioxidant and anthelmintic activity of selected traditional wild edible plants of lower Assam. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 48: 418-423. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0253-7613.186212>
32. Ullah A, Munir S, Badshah LS, Khan N, Ghani L, Poulson GB, Emwas HA, Jaremko M. (2020). Important flavonoids and their role as a therapeutic agent. *Molecules*, 25(22): 5243. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225243>
33. Jeong SM, Khosravi S, Mauliasari RI, Lee BJ, You SG, Lee MS. (2021). Nutritional evaluation of cricket, *Gryllus bimaculatus*, meal as fish meal substitute for olive flounder, *Paralichthys olivaceus* juveniles. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 52(4): 859-880. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12790>
34. Wang D, Zhai SW, Zhang CX, Bai YY, An SH, Xu YN. (2005). Evaluation on nutritional value of field crickets as a poultry feedstuff. *Asian-australasian journal of animal sciences*, 18(5): 667-670.